

transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing with 2 seedlings/hill. A uniform 40 kg N, 8.8 kg P/ha was applied at transplanting. The crop was irrigated as needed and harvested in the second week of Dec.

The grain yield differed among varieties and with date of transplanting (see table). Variety C62-68 and Janaki gave significantly higher yields (C62-68 grain weight was lower than that of Janaki, but it had more grains/ panicle).

Grain yield decreased significantly with delay in transplanting. The crop transplanted 16 Sep gave 27.6% lower grain yield than that transplanted 1 Sep; the 1 Oct crop gave 72.4% lower yield.

The variety by date of transplanting interaction also significantly influenced grain yield. Reduction in yield of C62-68 and Janaki due to delay in transplanting was less than that with other varieties.

Grain yield of double-transplanted, photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties by transplanting dates in flood-affected area of Pusa (Bihar), India.

	Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean
	1 Sep	16 Sep	1 Oct	
Janaki	3.6	2.7	1.2	2.5
BR8	2.2	2.2	0.9	1.8
T141	2.5	1.6	0.3	1.5
BR14	2.8	1.9	0.4	1.7
C62-68	3.8	3.0	1.5	2.8
Bakol (local check)	2.3	1.1	0.5	1.3
Mean	2.9	2.1	0.8	
LSD (0.05)				
For variety		0.3		
For date of transplanting		0.6		
For variety at same date of transplanting		0.5		
For date of transplanting of same variety		0.6		

Panicle exertion in the two varieties was complete even with the last transplanting date. This probably resulted in higher percentage of fertile spikelets in C62-68 and Janaki, and

consequently higher grain yields under extremely late transplanting. In other varieties, incomplete panicle exertion occurred with delay in transplanting. □

Effect of a new abscisic acid analog on chilled rice leaves

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One factor that limits rice growth and yield in many rice-growing countries is chilling injury. One measure to minimize this problem is chemical treatment. New abscisic acid analogs developed by BASF, Ludwigshafen, FRG, and coded LAB 173711 and LAB 144143 have been reported to increase chilling tolerance in cucumber, tomato, and wheat.

We investigated the effects of the analog in chilled rice leaves.

Pregerminated seeds of IR42 and Fujisaka 5 were seeded directly in 1-liter pot containing Maahas soil and kept at 29/21 °C, 12 h photoperiod, and 80% relative humidity. Uniform seedlings were selected and sprayed with LAB 173711 at 10⁻³ mol/liter, and 10⁻⁴ mol/liter. After 24 h, plants were transferred to 5 °C for 1, 2, 3, 5, and d. After chilling exposure, they were returned to 29 °C for recovery.

1. Percent leaf area injury in LAB 173711-treated rice plants chilled at 5 °C for 24 h and transferred to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 10 measurements.

Damaged leaf area was observed visually (wilted and brown color) and estimated using the formula

$$\text{Injured leaf area (\%)} = \frac{\text{length of injured portion}}{\text{length of whole leaf blade}} \times 100$$

2. Differences in leaf fresh weight of LAB 173711-treated plants chilled at 5 °C and transferred to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 10 measurements.

Injured leaf area was markedly lower in LAB 173711-treated plants (Fig. 1), and leaf fresh weight in control was much lower than in LAB 173711-treated plants (Fig. 2). This protective effect of the applied abscisic acid analog may be due in part to its water conserving-activity. □